

People's Perception towards Government Jobs in India: An Analytical Study of Delhi

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Abstract:

Unemployment has always been a problem in the growth of any nation because the prosperity of any country is determined by its per capita income. According Center for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE), India has gone far ahead in unemployment. Although the private and public sector both play a crucial role in solving this problem but in the economic culture of India, even today people give priority to government jobs which also becomes an important issue for governments at the time of elections. Along with government

jobs, people believe that it has several economic, social, and political benefits while it is hard to survive in private jobs. On the point of job satisfaction people's perception usually goes with government sector jobs, while some also consider private jobs to be more satisfactory as it gives exposure to all cutting-edge technology. Therefore, our aim in this paper is to find out the reasons why people prefer government jobs. For this, we have chosen an area like Delhi which is no less than a mini India. A sample of this region's people was selected for the study and a survey was applied to determine the factors that predict the perception of the people regarding government jobs.

Keywords: *Education, Government Job, Growth, Income-perks, Job security, Pension plans, Perception, Public Sector, Unemployment, Work flexibility.*

Introduction

Unemployment has been a characteristic of India for the last several decades. Every day hundreds of thousands of people leave their villages and migrate to cities for employment so that they can live a better life. Some are the most disturbing unemployment categories, which have created a growing concern among

legislators, the press, and professional economists, are those found among the educated and semi-skilled sections of the young community. It is difficult to estimate the extent of unemployment in these categories (Parthasarathy,1955). Unemployment in India has increased the demand for government employment to such an extent that a Ph.D. degree holder is even ready to do a peon's job

while the post required a minimum eligibility of Class V (Economic Times Online, 2018). People expect every upcoming government to provide government jobs on a large scale so that they can benefit. It is pretty much evident that the craze for government jobs is not intrinsic as they want to serve the nation or contribute to public services as such. This is because of the pull factor and the benefits associated with government jobs (Panagariya, 2020).

These benefits include less accountability, less workload, job security, less skill, and full salary. Despite this, it earns huge social respect for both the position holder and his family. Being in direct contact and relation with high bureaucrats and politicians gives people certain advantages in the power dynamics of society over other jobs. Apart from this, under the dowry system also a government job of a groom helps to increase his market value in marriage. Under the principle of the dowry system, the higher position (post) in the government job deserves a big dowry (Mota & Casaca, 2016).

On the contrary, in private jobs, a skill-based salary is provided. Wages are decided on productivity and innovations without having job security. It means private jobs are fully accountable to the offices without having a power position but hierarchical. Good perks and advantages are also given in such jobs but all those are based on work productivity and performance. Therefore, these jobs demand a workaholic person who may take the risk on his/her behalf. Most of the employees are kept on a contract basis. Not only this, workaholic people are also considered to be cut off from society. Maybe that's why people like these jobs less than government jobs and no need to say that this is considered as the last option if one does not get a government job in India (Bhandari & Heshmati, 2006). Thus, people have different perceptions about these realities so it becomes an important issue to know their perceptions towards government jobs. That's why this paper aims to explore the reasons behind this perception towards government jobs.

Review of Literature

Unemployment in India is seen as a national problem. It is attributed to the negative development of economic activities in the country. Despite of the execution of developmental plans by the governments, the number of unemployed people in developing countries increased very much. According to Padder & Mathavan (2021), the country has been facing these challenges since the 1980s when it was operating under a 'one-sector development model'. India took initiatives in the 1990s to curb the problem of rising unemployment and stagnant growth, but the implications of these policies have lagged behind economic and employment growth, leading to further unemployment, which has economists worried over the recent experience of portraying it as "unemployment-less growth" (Padder & Mathavan, 2021). Job placements were flourishing in private sectors but a pandemic like COVID shook this arrangement as well (Victor, Karakunnel, Loganathan, & Meyer, 2021) Due to this the social environment has changed because people were forced to think that if they had a government job, they would not have been removed from the job in private sectors. Although regarding job security, they used to give importance to government jobs even earlier but now expectations have risen (Zimmermann, 2024).

Perception means a particular way of looking at or understanding something (Cook, 2021). Sharmila Singh (2021) has pointed out a few factors that affect the perception. The First is PERCEPTUAL LEARNING where we learn from our past experiences. We tend to see and perceive things from our predefined knowledge. Second, MENTAL SET means giving special attention to something or being ready for any particular thing that makes us ready for it. Third, MOTIVES AND NEEDS simply means being motivated toward anything makes us think only way we can achieve our target. Just like a student preparing for an exam will only think of the exam and work on it. Fourth, COGNITIVE STYLE is of personal characteristics, where an individual's personality affects his attitude toward everything. Fifth, EXTRASENSORY

PERCEPTION is something that is not received by the senses. It could be said that gut feeling toward anything (Cook, 2021).

That is why people in India also have a different view regarding government jobs. Katherine V. Gough (2016) has argued that the youth are vulnerable regarding their jobs. They are the one who do not get jobs easily in the formal sector and even if they do they are the first to get fired. She argued that understanding youth and the transition toward adulthood are closely related to key life stages. She highlights that jobs are multidimensional. It brings significant change to who we are what work we do etc. therefore it is essential to focus on the employment of youth. If not worked on we will be wasting our productivity.

Determining why an individual would choose to work in the government sector rather than the private sector is a significant concern for public personnel management. With the quiet crisis in public administration, in which the government experiences difficulty in retaining employees, identifying why people select the government as their employer of choice to begin with is one means of better attracting, selecting, and retaining individuals for lifelong careers in government. To understand an individual's employment perceptions requires examining the larger organizational and management literature in a particular way.

Some factors or variables of government jobs could be observed. Several attributes play key roles in job selection by individuals. Carpenter & Strawser (1970) observed some attributes like-- Nature of work, Opportunities for advancement, Salary, Working condition, and job security (Carpenter & Strawser, 1971). Bundy & Norris (1992) added some more attributes such as Job security, Challenging and Interesting work, Advancement potential, Employer-paid health, Personalities of Supervisors and Co-workers (Bundy & Norris, 1992). McGinty & Reitsch (1992) has gone to the other points such as Location, Advancement, Social responsibility, Interest, Salary (McGinty & Reitsch, 1992). Browne (1997) observed some crucial attributes-Interesting or challenging

work, Salary, Sense of accomplishment, Chance of promotion, Stimulating/competent coworkers (Browne, 1997), whereas Butler et al. (2000) accounted some another attributes such as Compensation package, Opportunities for Advancement/Job stability, Type of Firm, Flex-Time, Work environment (Butler, Sanders & Whitecotton, 2000).

Apart from these elements Michael Christopher Moltz (2017) found some crucial factors such as job satisfaction (is often construed as a positive (or negative) evaluative judgment one makes about one's job or job situation which depends upon measuring an individual's perceptions of their work environment), organizational commitment (the impetus an individual has to contribute to an organization), performance (it can be distinguished between task performance and contextual performance. Task performance relates to the job at hand, while contextual performance has effects beyond simply carrying out the duties of one's job), Extrinsic motives (these motives are often driven by external rewards such as high pay, benefits, job security, or status within an organization), intrinsic motives (this motivation is based on the internal satisfaction one gets from completing a task which usually associated with the private sector), public service motivation (in which people choose government employment is due to their desires to "serve the public interest) (Moltz, 2017).

By looking at all these variables we have arrived at the following conceptual framework (Figure 1).

Purpose of the Study

1. To find out the factors that are responsible for making the people's perception toward government jobs.
2. To analyze the factors responsible for the perception of people toward government jobs.

Hypotheses

H₀: The factors related to people perception are not correlated with variables related to government job.

H₁: The variables related to the government job have no impact on people perception.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Methodology

Delhi includes people from different regions, religions, castes, creeds, ethnicities, and sex and income backgrounds. It is also a power hub of India as it is the capital of India. This makes it the house of central government and state government employees. It is surrounded by National Capital Regions (NCR). This is highly populated with versatile cultures and people. It also has a slum as per the Delhi Urban Shelter Improvement Board there are 675 slums in

Delhi. Not only that but it is surrounded by high-tech cities and areas like cyber city Guru Gram, Faridabad, and many industrial areas. So Delhi is a perfect place where we can gather our data and analyze it for our study to know the perception of Indian people towards government jobs. This empirical research is exploratory and descriptive in nature based on primary data. The primary data was collected through online survey in the form of questionnaire includes both open ended and close ended. The survey was conducted by Google form. The Likert scale questionnaire was applied to the willingness of the people in survey with respondents' acceptance.(See table 2).

Result and Discussion

For any research, it is very important to know the internal consistency between items in different variables. The reliability of a questionnaire or data is examined by Cronbach's alpha. It represents the consistency and reliability of the data. Here, Cronbach's alpha is 0.804 which is above 0.80 for 25 items, on behalf of this, data can be considered normal and reliable. Now we could apply a parametric test to the data. If Cronbach's alpha value is more than 0.7 then it is considered as acceptable whereas the high level of alpha shows the items in the test are highly correlated so in our study it shows that our items are highly correlated. (See table 1)

Table 1. Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
	.804	25

Table 2. Demographic Information

Variables	Description of Items	Frequency	Percent
Age	18-25 Years	183	94.3
	26-40 Years	4	2.1
	41-60 Years	7	3.6
Gender	Male	129	66.5
	Female	65	33.5
Marital Status	Single	184	94.8
	Married	10	5.2

Educational Qualification	No formal qualification	2	1.0
	Secondary	3	1.5
	Higher Secondary	13	6.7
	Undergraduate	128	66.0
	Graduate	35	18.0
	Post Graduate	9	4.6
	Post Graduate and Above	4	2.1
Occupation	Student	167	86.1
	Unemployed	7	3.6
	Home Makers	2	1.0
	Private Employed	8	4.1
	Self-employed/Business person	3	1.5
	Govt. Employed	7	3.6
Family Income	Rs.10000-20000	60	30.9
	Rs.21000-50000	48	24.7
	Rs.51000-100000	52	26.8
	Above Rs.100000	34	17.5
	Total	194	100.0

Table 2 represents the majority of the respondents of males (66.5) of 18-25 Years age-wise (94.3) who are single (94.8) undergraduate (66.0) students (86.1) whose family income is between Rs.10000-20000.

Table 3. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.710
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1387.827
	df	300
	Sig.	.000

Table 3 illustrates the value of The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test is equal to 0.710 > 0.6 which represents that sampling is adequate and the factor analysis is worthwhile for the data set. Bartlett's test of Sphericity also represents the adequacy of the correlation matrix. This test is found highly significant at $p < 0.001$ which shows that the correlation matrix has significant correlations among at least some of the variables. Here the test value is 1387.827 and an associated degree of significance is less than 0.0001. Results represent variables are highly correlated to each other which reject the Hypothesis 1 (H_0).

Table 4. Communalities Matrix

	Initial	Extraction
Most of the people prefer govt. Job in India	1.000	.677
People feel that govt. job is related to the power factor	1.000	.696
Govt. job provides financial security	1.000	.617
Govt. job provides guaranteed promotion	1.000	.658
Govt. job gives positive feedback to the work of employee	1.000	.649
Govt. job shows satisfied past experience	1.000	.734
People are willing to apply for lower rank govt. jobs	1.000	.606
There is no need of pre requisite skill in government job although it is desirable	1.000	.652
People are willing to opt coaching to get any government job.	1.000	.644
People are ready to grab the government job whether it is far away from their residence.	1.000	.695
Govt. job has limited work hours in daily routine.	1.000	.733
In Govt. job employees feel less work pressure.	1.000	.729
Govt. job gives better retirement benefits in comparison to private job.	1.000	.598
Govt. job provides handsome salary.	1.000	.721
Government job has least accountability in work culture.	1.000	.683

People have specific attention towards government job upcoming vacancies/advertisements.	1.000	.726
Most of the families want government job for their children to secure their future.	1.000	.682
Government job offer source of extra income.	1.000	.622
Government job are easy to get for weaker section.	1.000	.659
Government jobs are less productive	1.000	.626
Government jobs gives social status	1.000	.631
I will prepare for government job, as reliable career option.	1.000	.678
Government Job provides job security and stability.	1.000	.697
Government job provides the platform for the future growth and opportunity.	1.000	.708
Government job provides enough time to employees to look after their families.	1.000	.657
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

The communality matrix is used to find common factors because the proportion of common variance within a variable is treated as the communality. That's why, before any extraction, all of the variance related to a variable is assumed as a common variance while after extraction the communalities show the degree of variance in each variable that can be explained by the retained factors. The table 4 shows that 60% and above of the variance related to these items is

common in the extraction column of the communalities. Communality matrix represents that almost all factors of government job are related to the people perception except retirement benefits and People are willing to apply for lower rank govt. jobs. Result of the analysis indicated about 18 factors with eigenvalue greater than 0.6. For the reporting, these factors could be considered as appropriate which have more than 0.6. Value.

Table 5. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.607 ^a	.368	.330	4.21933

Note: a. Predictors: (Constant), Offer source of extra income, Look after their families, families prefer govt. job, Less productive, least accountability, Govt job gives better retirement benefits, Reliable career option, Future growth and opportunity, Social Status, Enough time, Job security

Table 6. ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1889.835	11	171.803	9.650	.000 ^b
	Residual	3240.099	182	17.803		
	Total	5129.934	193			

Note: a: Dependent Variable: Var_Perception; b: Predictors: (Constant), Offer source of extra income, Look after their families, families prefer govt. job, Less productive, least accountability, Govt job gives better retirement benefits, Reliable career option, Future growth and opportunity, Social Status, Enough time, Job security.

Table 7. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	22.521	2.990		7.531	.000
	Govt. job gives better retirement benefits in comparison to private job.	.993	.402	.168	2.467	.015

	Govt. job provides handsome salary.	.214	.416	.039	.514	.608
	Government job has least accountability in work culture.	.854	.378	.154	2.256	.004
	Most of the families want government job for their children to secure their future.	1.566	.525	.214	2.985	.003
	Government jobs are less productive	.593	.335	.115	1.772	.078
	Government jobs gives social status	-.055	.579	-.007	-.096	.924
	I will prepare for government job, as reliable career option.	.110	.340	.023	.322	.748
	Government Job provides job security and stability.	.506	.686	.060	.738	.462
	Government job provides the platform for the Future growth and opportunity.	-.280	.432	-.051	-.649	.517
	Government job provides enough time to employees to look after their families.	1.524	.384	.269	3.969	.000
	Government job offer source of extra income.	.992	.350	.187	2.836	.005

Note: a. Dependent Variable: Var_Perception

The Regression coefficient 'R'² = .607^a or 60.7% represents that the correlation between dependent and independent variables is positive. The coefficient of determination 'R Square' = 0.368 explaining that 36.8% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable (indicating in Table 5). F-Test Value 9.650 is significant because the significant level is =.000 (ANOVA table no 6 is indicating). This also means that correlation between the dependent and independent variables is statistically significant and regression model is valid. Regression model table clears that the variables related to the government job have an impact on people perception. The variables related to the government job positively related and highly effects the perception of the people. Hence the study rejects the null hypothesis (H₁).

Standardized Coefficients table indicates the relative influence of people's perception towards the government job on predictors. The highest number of Beta is 0.269 (table 7) for 'Government job provides enough time to employees to look after their families' which is significant at the 0.000 level. 'Most of the families want government job for their children to secure their future' dimension also reflects a

considerable amount of Beta which is 0.214 and is also significant at the 0.000 level (which is 0.003). 'Government job offer source of extra income' is also reflecting the considerable amount of Beta which is 0.187 and is also significant at the 0.000 level (which is 0.005). 'Government job has least accountability in work culture' is also reflecting the considerable amount of Beta which is 0.154 and is also significant at the 0.000 level (which is 0.004). This shows that there is a positive relationship between government job's variables and people's perception with the influence of government job variables on the people's perception.

Conclusion

The main objective of the study was to find out the factors that are responsible for making the people's perception toward government jobs. Based on the finding it can be argued that significant factors of govt. jobs were found interrelated or correlated to the people perception. Results shows that India's people prefer govt. job, they feel govt. job is associated with power factor. They believe that govt. job

provides financial security, guaranteed promotion, positive feedback to the work of employee, job satisfaction, handsome salary, social status, job security and stability, provides the platform for the future growth and opportunity, and provides enough time to employees to look after their families. That's why people are willing to apply for lower rank govt. jobs because they believe that there is no need of pre requisite skill in government job although it is desirable. They are ready to grab the government job whether it is far away from their residence. People are willing to opt coaching to get any government job. That's why People have specific attention towards government job upcoming vacancies/advertisements. Because they believe that govt. jobs are less productive and these have limited work hours in daily routine, employees feel less work pressure with least accountability in work culture. Just because of these reasons people consider govt. job as reliable career option and they want government job for their children to secure their future, but by the analysis of the factors responsible for the perception of the towards government jobs. Result shows that four factors are highly responsible for making people perception towards the govt. jobs such as people highly believe that Government job provides enough time to employees to look after their families, Government job offer source of extra income with least accountability in work culture that's why most of the families want government job for their children to secure their future. There are a few limitations of the study that the collection of the data for this study was limited to Delhi's single, undergraduate, male, student, who comes under the age between 18-25 Years. Hence, generalization of the findings is limited to a similar context and comparable population of group. Despite these limitations, the study provided the base for the conclusion to be established and it can be concluded that people want govt. job in India just because of provides enough time for employees to look after their families and offers a source of extra income with the least accountability in work culture so that their children may secure their future which is underlying in a negative sense.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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